

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY AND EMPLOYMENT

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Abstract. *The digitalization of the economy is opening up vast opportunities in many countries today. In particular, the digital economy not only creates numerous opportunities for the population but also plays a crucial role in the socio-economic development of the state. This article discusses the advantages of the digital economy and its role in reducing the shadow economy and informal employment.*

Key words: *digital economy, shadow economy, informal employment, e-government, economic growth, labor productivity.*

Introduction: In many countries around the world, the introduction of e-government began with the emergence of new technologies. Although there are various debates on this issue, e-government is generally defined as the use of ICT to improve the functioning of public sector organizations. As a result of advanced technological tools, "E-government aims to enhance relations between people and their governments by improving the efficiency of service delivery, ensuring easy access for all, considering people's needs, increasing public participation in decision-making, and enhancing the transparency and accountability of state institutions."¹

The demand for labor is expected to increase for innovative products and services, whereas the opposite can be expected for more standardized products. For example, Rifkin argues that in the future, the digital revolution will significantly reduce employment, as he considers the marginal cost of production to be close to zero². This means that even a low-wage worker would be more expensive than the additional costs required to operate a smart machine. However, this pessimistic scenario can only materialize if the level of production remains unchanged..

We are witnessing the rapid expansion of new opportunities for entrepreneurship and self-employment in the digital economy. In many cases, investments aimed at developing ICT have resulted in economic growth, the creation of new jobs, the emergence of new services for the population and businesses, and the reduction of government administration costs within e-government projects. The advantages of horizontal networks over hierarchical ones—primarily

¹ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2020 йил 28 апрелдаги “Рақамли иқтисодиёт ва электрон ҳукуматни кенг жорий этиш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида” ПҚ-4699-сонли қарори.

² Policies to Reduce Informal Employment. An International Survey. Technical Note for the Government of Ukraine. The World Bank - 2011. – 17 p.

due to their higher exchange speed and diversity—serve as the foundation for a new phase of economic growth.

The 2016 ILO study, “Non-Standard Employment Around the World: Understanding Challenges, Shaping Prospects”, explored various perspectives on the relationship between new technologies and informality. Some studies focus on the emergence of new forms of informality, particularly the rise of non-standard employment. Others examine the processes and challenges faced by informal sector entities in adopting new technologies into their businesses or activities.

Additionally, some researchers analyze the impact of technology on productivity and informality. Moreover, there is an increasing view that the distinction between formal and informal employment is becoming less clear, making these categories increasingly difficult to differentiate.³

As a result of analyzing various characteristics of the digital economy that may impact the labor market, the following figure highlights its strengths and opportunities.

1–picture. The impact of the digital economy on the labor market

Source: Compiled by the author.

The formation of a digitalized economy has distinct characteristics, primarily defined by the expansion and systematization of digital content (the object of labor) and the automatic creation of added value without human intervention. One of the key features of the digital economy is the speed of change in practical business models and management within the production of goods and services.

Although Table 1 presents the potential economic and social benefits of digitalizing the economy, all studies highlight that this "revolution" has a significant impact on the labor market.

³ Schneider F. New Estimates for the Shadow Economies all over the World / F. Schneider, A. Buehn, C.E. Montenegro // International Economic Journal. – 2010. – №24 (4). P. 443-461.

Table 1.

The economic and social impact of digitalizing the economy

Economic benefit	Social benefit
1. Significant contribution to economic growth	1. Increased inclusivity and reduction of poverty
2. Sharp reduction in bureaucratic processes, corruption, and bribery	2. Time-saving benefits
3. Decrease in the level of the shadow economy and informal employment	3. Improved access to and quality of healthcare services
4. Increase in labor productivity	4. Lower costs and greater accessibility of mass education
5. Acceleration of small and medium-sized business growth	5. Reduced negative impact on the environment
6. Growth in job opportunities in related industries	6. Decrease in crime rates and enhanced public safety
7. Expanded and easier access to financial services	7. Expanded opportunities for developing countries
8. Reduction of market entry barriers for products and businesses	

Source: Compiled by the author

Based on the above, it can be concluded that the digital economy plays a crucial role not only in public administration but also in the formation of a new economic structure, the emergence of an information-based society, and the reduction of the shadow economy and informal employment. The provision of government services through the digital economy ensures the following:

- Reduction of budget expenditures;
- Simplification of public service delivery (e.g., obtaining information, permits, etc.);
- Decrease in bureaucracy and corruption;
- Free access to essential government data and reduced interaction time between citizens and government officials;
- Continuous expansion of electronic public services available to the population;
- Increased public trust in government institutions, among other benefits.

In Uzbekistan, starting from January 1, 2020, a "Unified National Labor System" was introduced to register new employment contracts, modify existing ones, and record contract terminations.

Additionally, an electronic labor book was implemented, automatically generating employee work activity records⁴. Moreover, the system requires inputting data on available job vacancies, aiming to reduce unemployment, improve service quality for job seekers, and formalize labor relations for informal workers. The system also focuses on enhancing vocational training and retraining programs, particularly for youth and women, by actively utilizing information and communication technologies (ICT) in project development.

Table 2⁵

The annual volume of gross added value generated in the information economy and e-commerce sector (in billion UZS)

This table presents the gross added value generated in Uzbekistan's information economy and e-commerce sector. Over the years, its volume has increased due to ongoing efforts and reforms, reflecting the development of the digital economy in the country. At the same time, some governments are actively adapting to new technologies in the public sector, particularly in the labor market, and are using digital tools to facilitate the formalization of economic entities and employment.

In the context of Uzbekistan, the digitalization of the economy has a significant impact on employment. Digital technologies enable job optimization, increase labor productivity, and reduce informal employment. While some traditional professions may disappear due to new technologies, new professions such as IT specialists, e-commerce professionals, and digital service providers are emerging.

The digital economy enhances labor market flexibility and expands opportunities for remote work (e.g., freelancing and telecommuting). Additionally, e-government systems reduce bureaucracy and encourage people to participate in formal employment relationships.

⁴ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2019 йил 31 октябрдаги “Ягона миллий меҳнат тизими” идоралараро дастурий-аппарат комплексини жорий қилиш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида”ги ПҚ 4502-сонли қарори.

⁵ Muallif ishlanmasi. Manba:stat.uz

In Uzbekistan, the launch of platforms like the "Unified National Labor System" has contributed to increasing formal employment rates.

However, to fully harness the benefits of digitalization, the following aspects must be addressed:

- Training and retraining of personnel – Developing a skilled workforce that meets the demands of the digital economy.
- Development of ICT infrastructure – Expanding internet access and improving IT services.
- Encouraging the transition from the informal to the formal sector – Strengthening the legal framework for e-commerce and labor relations.

In conclusion, in Uzbekistan, the digitalization of the economy not only increases employment but also leads to qualitative changes in job structures. Therefore, a well-implemented state policy that adapts to technological transformations will maximize the positive impact of the digital economy on the labor market.

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